

“Morphometric analysis of the Late Cretaceous *Placenticerus* of Alabama, USA: Sexual dimorphism, allometry, and implications for taxonomy”

SUPPLEMENT TEXT

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***Placenticer*s taxa reported from the eastern Gulf Coastal Plain**

Below, we list all 14 species and varieties of *Placenticer*s that have been previously reported from the eastern Gulf Coastal Plain, presenting each as a member of the *Placenticer*s genus, regardless of the generic or subgeneric assignment (e.g., *Stantonoceras*) in the cited publications, as opinions and usage have varied.

- (1) *Placenticer*s *syrtale* Morton (1834). The holotype of *P. syrtale*, as figured by Morton (1834) is from Greene County, AL. Kennedy et al. (1997) additionally report *P. syrtale* from Monroe and Lowndes Counties, MS. One of their reported occurrences of *P. syrtale* (USGS Mesozoic 32145) was listed erroneously as Lowndes County, AL, but describes a location in Lowndes County, MS (Tibbee Creek).
- (2) *Placenticer*s *syrtale* var. *halei* Hyatt (1903). Hyatt (1903) named this variety based on specimens from Greene County, AL.
- (3) *Placenticer*s *guadalupae* Roemer (1852). Reported from Alabama and Georgia (Stephenson 1914) and from Mississippi (Stephenson 1914; Stephenson and Monroe 1940), but not figured or described in those publications. *P. guadalupae* is now often synonymized under *P. syrtale* (e.g., Wolleben 1967).
- (4) *Placenticer*s *spillmani* Hyatt (1903). The holotype by monotypy of Hyatt's (1903) *P. spillmani* is a fragment from Mississippi.
- (5) *Placenticer*s *placenta* DeKay (1828). Well-documented occurrences of *P. placenta* were reported by Kennedy et al. (1997) in Mississippi. Additional Mississippi occurrences were reported by Sohl (1964) and Dockery (1991). Reported occurrences in Alabama have not been supported by described or figured specimens (Hilgard 1860; Hyatt 1903) and were considered questionable by Reeside (1927).
- (6) *Placenticer*s *placenta* var. *hyatti* Stephenson (1923). Stephenson reported an occurrence of *P. placenta* var. *hyatti* in Perry County, AL.

- (7) *Placenticerus planum* Hyatt (1903). Reported from Alabama (Stephenson 1914) and Mississippi (Stephenson 1914; Stephenson and Monroe 1940), but not figured or described in those publications. Reeside (1927) doubted all reported occurrences of *P. planum* from the Gulf Coast States, but Young (1963) did not, and reiterated the likely occurrence of *P. planum* in Lowndes County, MS.
- (8) *Placenticerus benningi* Stephenson (1956). The holotypes and paratypes of Stephenson (1956) are from the Chattahoochee region of Alabama and Georgia. Schwimmer et al. (1985) reiterate the occurrence of *P. benningi* in Georgia, but do not describe or figure any specimens.
- (9) *Placenticerus pseudosyrtae* Hyatt (1903). Young (1963) reports that there are specimens of *P. pseudosyrtae* from Lowndes County, MS in the collections of the U.S. National Museum, but does not describe or figure those specimens. *P. pseudosyrtae* is commonly considered synonymous with *P. syrtae* (e.g., Wolleben 1967).
- (10) *Placenticerus pseudocostatum* Johnson (1903). Young (1963) reports that “two unusual morphotypes, one of which is probably *Placenticerus costatum* Johnson (1904 [sic, refers to a reprint of Johnson’s 1903 publication]), that have always been included in *P. planum*, s. l., are also present in Lowndes County [Mississippi] and in the San Carlos area [Texas].” Young was probably referring to *P. pseudocostatum* Johnson (1903), rather than *P. costatum* Hyatt (1903), although *P. pseudocostatum* is commonly synonymized with *P. syrtae* rather than with *P. planum* (e.g., Reeside 1927; Wolleben 1967; Kennedy et al. 2004). Regardless, Young does not describe or figure any specimens from Lowndes County, so this occurrence is questionable.
- (11) ‘early’ *Placenticerus meeki* Böhm (1898). Young (1963) reports “early *P. meeki*” occurring as part of a “peculiar *Placenticerus* fauna” in Lowndes County, MS, but does not describe or figure any specimens, so this occurrence is questionable.
- (12) *Placenticerus sancarlosense* Hyatt (1903). Young (1963) reports *P. sancarlosense* occurring in Lowndes County, MS, but does not describe or figure any specimens. *P. sancarlosense* is commonly synonymized with *P. syrtae* (e.g., Wolleben 1967).

- (13) *Placenticerus polyopsis* Dujardin (1837). Kennedy and Wright (1983) note that W.A. Cobban considered some *Placenticerus* specimens from the Eutaw Formation of Alabama to be referable to *P. polyopsis*, a possibility reiterated by Kennedy (1987) and Gangopadhyay and Bardhan (2007). Notably, Hyatt (1903) considered his specimens of *P. syrtale* var. *halei* from Greene County, AL to be comparable to *P. polyopsis*.
- (14) *Placenticerus* n. sp. Young (early 2000s, unpublished). In an unpublished manuscript on the Upper Cretaceous ammonites of Alabama, the late Dr. Keith Young designated a new species of *Placenticerus* based on five specimens from the Ripley Formation of Alabama. Due to the distortion of the specimens from sedimentary load or diagenesis, Young refrained from naming the species, but compared it to *P. intercalare* and *P. meeki*. Young additionally comments that he was tempted to name a new subspecies for *P. planum* based on the specimens he examined from the Tombigbee Sand Member of the Eutaw Formation in Alabama.

***Placenticerus* Temporal Range**

In the existing literature, there are mixed reports on the upper limit for the range of *Placenticerus*, with some workers reporting a last occurrence in the Campanian (e.g., Cobban 2016; Gangopadhyay and Bardhan 2007; Waggoner 2006; Bardhan et al. 2002; Wright 1996) and others reporting a last occurrence in the Maastrichtian (e.g., Cobban 1993; Klinger and Kennedy 1989; Kennedy and Wright 1983; Stephenson 1941). None of the above reports of Maastrichtian *Placenticerus* are still valid, since the ages of those occurrences have since been revised, and they are now all considered to be Campanian. Cobban (1993) reported *Placenticerus* from the *B. reesidei* Zone in the Western Interior of North America, then considered to be Maastrichtian, but now considered to be Late Campanian (e.g., Kennedy et al. 2000). Stephenson's (1941) evidence for a Maastrichtian occurrence of *Placenticerus* was the occurrence of *Placenticerus meeki* and *P. intercalare* in the Neylandville Marl of Texas. However, more recent studies using ammonite biostratigraphy now place the Neylandville Marl within the Upper Campanian *B. compressus* and *B. cuneatus* Zones (Larson 2016). Kennedy and Wright (1983) and Klinger and Kennedy

(1989) extended the range of *Placenticerus* into the Maastrichtian on the sole basis of the inclusion in its synonymy of the genus *Gissarites* Iljin (1958) from Central Asia, which reportedly occurred in the Maastrichtian (Iljin 1958, 1959). However, more recent publications have revised the known occurrences of *Gissarites* (including the original holotype specimens of the type species *G. kysylchense*) to include only Campanian strata (Atabekyan and Khakimov 1976; Iljin 2000). The Campanian age for *Gissarites* eliminates the need to extend the range of *Placenticerus* into the Maastrichtian.

The only Maastrichtian occurrence of *Placenticerus* that has not been revised to a Campanian age is the recent report of *P. meeki* and *P. costatum* from the earliest Maastrichtian *Baculites baculus* zone from the Raton Basin of New Mexico, USA (Sealey and Lucas 2022); those authors extend the temporal range of *Placenticerus* into the earliest Maastrichtian in the Western Interior. To our knowledge, there are no other well-documented Maastrichtian occurrences of *Placenticerus* anywhere else in North America or worldwide that have yet been reported.

Potential Maastrichtian occurrences of *Placenticerus* in the eastern Gulf Coastal Plain

Although *Placenticerus* is not known to occur above the Upper Campanian anywhere outside of the Western Interior (e.g., Sealey and Lucas 2022), the locality information associated with 36 (18%) of our studied specimens suggests the possibility of a Maastrichtian occurrence in the eastern Gulf Coastal Plain. Two specimens are reportedly from locations with outcrops of the Maastrichtian Providence Sand (Youngblood, AL and northeast Butler County, AL), but their precise collection locality or whether they were collected in-situ is unknown. Neither of these two specimens were well-preserved enough to include in our morphological analyses.

Two specimens from the Fort Benning area in Georgia are reportedly from the Maastrichtian Prairie Bluff Formation, but the Prairie Bluff Formation thins out in eastern Alabama and does not occur in Georgia (Donovan et al. 1988). We designate the geological formation for these specimens as “unknown.” An additional thirteen specimens from Alabama were labeled as “Prairie Bluff,” which likely refers to the Prairie Bluff locality in Wilcox County rather than the Prairie Bluff Formation, since these specimens were all collected in the 19th Century. The upper Ripley Formation is also present at the Prairie

Bluff locality (Mancini et al. 1989) and early collectors often labeled specimens from these “ferruginous sands” simply as “Prairie Bluff” (e.g., Morton 1834), leading later workers to sometimes misinterpret the reported horizon of these fossils as the more specific Prairie Bluff Chalk. While the upper Ripley Formation is now also considered to be Maastrichtian in age (Mancini et al. 1989; Mancini et al. 1996; Mancini and Puckett 2005), most of our historic “Prairie Bluff” specimens are small, worn fragments, and may represent specimens recently transported from older strata upstream. In this study, we take a conservative approach and label the geological formation for these 13 specimens as “unknown.”

Additionally, nineteen specimens from localities in Lowndes and Barbour Counties, Alabama are from the Ripley Formation. The upper part of the Ripley Formation is considered to be Lower Maastrichtian (e.g., Mancini and Puckett 2005), but our studied specimens do not have sufficiently detailed horizon information to confirm which part of the Ripley Formation they were collected from. Reworking of older fossils in the Ripley Formation could also have occurred, due to its nearshore depositional environment (Harrell et al. 2016). Considering the lack of well-documented and in-situ occurrences of *Placenticer*s specimens from Maastrichtian horizons in our study area, we refrain from extending the temporal range of the genus within the eastern Gulf Coastal Plain, but acknowledge that future work in the eastern Gulf Coastal Plain may reveal Maastrichtian *Placenticer*s occurrences.

Fully septate *Placenticer*s specimens

“Fully septate” individuals represent fossil specimens for which the collected phragmocone is completely divided by septa, indicating that the body chamber (which is present at all life stages) was not preserved. The lack of a preserved body chamber or mature modifications present on the specimen does not preclude the possibility that the fossil represents the inner whorls of an adult individual, but it does indicate that—at the whorl height size where measurements were taken—the individual had not yet reached maturity or terminal growth.

Additional ornament terminology and variables

In this study, we use the term “tubercle” as a general term for any ornamental protrusion on the studied *Placenticer* specimens (including bullae or clavae). The varying taphonomic wear on our specimens makes it difficult to consistently assess the original shape of some ornamentation and to compare them between specimens. Therefore, we refer to all ornamentation as “tubercles” even in cases when we can identify a more precise form, such as the longitudinally elongated clavae commonly observed on many *Placenticer* venters. We distinguish between three tubercle locations, based on their position on the conch: umbilical tubercles (UTs), forming the inner row of tubercles on the flank, the lateral tubercles (LTs), forming the outer row of tubercles on the flank, and the ventral tubercles (VTs), positioned on either edge of the venter.

We could not reliably count tubercle frequency per half or quarter whorl but could often determine whether a given type of tubercle was present or absent on each measured position of the conch. For umbilical and ventral tubercles (UTs and VTs), we recorded simple presence/absence information (or “unknown” when taphonomy prevented a clear determination), but for lateral tubercles (LTs), we distinguished between two types of present LTs: “true” tubercles (prominent node or bulla), and “low swellings,” which are subtle rib-like undulations that can be felt on the surface of the flank (a feature previously described in *Placenticer*; see Cobban 2016).

Linear Mixed Models (LMMs): Methods

“Random Intercept Models”

The single-slope “Random Intercept Models” modelled variation in each response variable as:

$$\log(y_{ij}) = \alpha + \beta \cdot \log(\text{WH}_{ij}) + u_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

$$u_i \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2), \varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

Where y_{ij} is the value of the response variable for each specimen i at sampling location j , coefficient α represents the intercept, coefficient β represents the slope of the response variable on $\log(\text{WH})$, and u_i are individual-specific random intercepts assumed to follow a normal distribution with a mean of zero and a variance to be estimated. Lastly, LMMs assume errors, ε_{ij} , follow a normal distribution.

“Random Slope Models”

The “Random Slope Models” modelled variation in each response variable as:

$$\log(y_{ij}) = \alpha + \beta \log(\text{WH}_{ij}) + u_{1i} + u_{2i} \log(\text{WH}_{ij}) + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_{1i} \\ u_{2i} \end{pmatrix} \sim MVN(0, \psi), \varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

Where y_{ij} is the value of the response variable for each specimen i at sampling location j . Coefficient α represents the intercept. Coefficient β represents the slope of the response variable on $\log(\text{WH})$. Lastly, u_{1i} and u_{2i} are individual-specific random intercept and slope effects. The random slopes and intercepts allow both the mean (intercept) value of each response variable and the rate of change in the response variable with increasing $\log(\text{WH})$ to vary across specimens and were assumed to follow a multivariate normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a variance-covariance matrix to be estimated.

“Threshold Models”

The threshold LMMs described variation in each response variable as:

$$\log(y_{ij}) = \alpha + \beta_1 \log(\text{WH}_{ij}) + \beta_2 (\log(\text{WH}_{ij}) - T_1)_+ + u_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

$$u_i \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2), \varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

Where y_{ij} is the value of the response variable for specimen i at sampling location j . Threshold value T_1 varied across candidate models for each response variable and $(\log(\text{WH}_{ij}) - T_1)_+$ represents the product of $(\log(\text{WH}_{ij}) - T_1)$ and a logical function $(+)$ equal to 1 when $\log(\text{WH}_{ij}) > T_1$ and 0 otherwise. Coefficient β_1 represents the slope of each response variable on $\log(\text{WH})$ at small whorl heights ($\log(\text{WH}) \leq T_1$) and β_2 represents the change in slope after the threshold size. The slope after the threshold can be calculated from the coefficient estimates as $\beta_1 + \beta_2$. The logical function toggles the β_2 term *off* for sizes $\leq T_1$ and *on* for whorl heights $>$ than T_1 . Lastly, u_i are individual-specific random intercepts and ε_{ij} are normally-distributed errors.

A note on the allometry of size-standardized variables

No size-standardized variables (linear measurement variables divided by WH) were included as response variables in our LMMs, because the log-log relationship of the size-standardized variable with

WH can be directly inferred from the log-log relationship of the associated linear measurement variable with WH. A slope of 1 on a log-log scale indicates isometry between the linear measurement variable and WH (constant scaling of two size measures), which is equivalent to a slope of zero on a log-log scale for isometry between the size-standardized variable and WH (no correlation between “shape” and size) (Klingenberg 2016, pg. 118). This relationship is demonstrated using allometric equation:

$$y_1 = b(WH)^\alpha \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

Where y_1 is the linear measurement variable (var). When log-transformed, this equation results in the linear relationship:

$$\log(y_1) = \alpha \cdot \log(WH) + \log(b) \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

This equation is modeled by the LMM using the log-transformed linear measurement variable as the response variable, and $\log(WH)$ as the independent variable, with the resulting slope represented by α .

We can model the size-standardized variable (var/WH) as y_2 :

$$y_2 = \frac{y_1}{WH} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

Substituting y_2 into the original allometric equation results in:

$$y_2 = b(WH)^{\alpha-1} \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

Once log-transformed, the above equation becomes a linear relationship:

$$\log(y_2) = (\alpha - 1) \cdot \log(WH) + \log(b) \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

When comparing equations 2 and 5, it is demonstrated that the slope of the log-log relationship between the size-standardized variable and WH will be one less than the slope of the log-log relationship between the original linear measurement variable and WH. Consequently, an allometric relationship in equation 2 (a slope of 1) will be equivalent to a constant scaling relationship (slope of zero) in equation 5. We observed this relationship empirically for our data when comparing LMM models with either the linear measurement variable or the size-standardized variable as the log-transformed response variable, further justifying our decision to only analyze the results of LMMs performed on the original linear measurement variables (see, for example, Supplementary Figure 1 and Supplementary Table 1, which

present the results of two LMM models utilizing either $\log(WW)$ or $\log(WW/WH)$ as the response variable).

Linear Mixed Models: Results

“Temporal Models” and Power Analyses

The coefficient estimates and sample sizes for each geological formation “factor level” of our “Temporal Model” LMMs are shown in Supplementary Tables 7 and 8. The results of our power analysis simulations of the “Temporal Model” LMMs are shown in Supplementary Figures 9 and 10 (see also main text Section 3.3.3. “Bivariate Analyses: Extending LMMs to Evaluate Temporal Patterns”). Supplementary Table 6 reports the standard deviation (SD) for each variable used as the “medium” effect size for the power analyses (Supplementary Figs. 9 and 10). For dimensionless variables, SD is the standard deviation of the log-transformed variable; for linear measurement variables, SD is the standard deviation of the log-transformed size-standardized variable.

Log-transformation of dimensionless variables in PCA

Supplementary Figure 2 demonstrates the minimal impact on our “main PCA” (main text Figs. 10 and 11) of log-transforming only the linear measurement variables versus all variables before analysis. A comparison of panels A and C shows that the PC1-PC2 morphospace of projected individuals is similar under the two scenarios, as is the strength and direction of all variable vectors. A comparison of panels B and D (the PC2-PC3 morphospace) also shows similar results under both scenarios. Note that the direction of a given principal component axis is arbitrary; results are equivalent when flipping the results of the projection across either principal component axis.

Main PCA: Alternative Variable Sets

Our “main PCA” (main text Figs. 10 & 11) included a combination of linear measurement variables and size-standardized or dimensionless variables. Here we show two alternative PCAs using the same data ($n=105$ specimens) but with different combinations of variables included in the analysis: (1) a “linear PCA” including only linear measurement variables and (2) a “shape PCA” including only size-

standardized and dimensionless variables and log-transformed WH. In contrast to our “main PCA”, the alternative PCAs did a poor job of capturing both size and shape information within the same PCA while still performing well under the data imputation algorithm.

“Linear PCA”: Results

The “linear PCA” was run on the same data subset as our “main PCA” (i.e., the same measured positions for n=105 specimens) but included only the linear measurement variables: WH, WW, U, and VW (all log-transformed). This dataset had a total of 20.5% missing values. For the “linear PCA,” only the first two principal components were retained; both explained $\geq 10\%$ of the total variance in the data and collectively they explained 98.5% of the total variance. The third principal component explained only 0.9% of the total variance and was not visualized. PC1 explained most variance in the data (90.5%) and was dominated by specimen size (Supplementary Fig. 11). PC2 (explaining 8% of the total variance) captured variation in relative venter width, with VW loading positively on this component and WH loading negatively on this component; similar to results from the “main PCA,” individuals with positive PC2 scores have relatively wider venters.

For the “linear PCA” data, the most frequently-supported number of clusters was two (optimal under eight of 30 cluster validity indices), followed by three clusters (optimal under seven of the cluster validity indices). The projection of the 2- and 3-cluster scenarios into the ordination space of our “linear PCA” are shown in Supplementary Figure 11. For clarity, we will refer to specific clusters in each of the “linear PCA” scenarios using the names assigned to them in Supplementary Figure 11. In both the 2- and 3-cluster scenarios, the clusters were distinguished by specimen size.

“Linear PCA”: Discussion

The “linear PCA” dataset, which included only linear measurement variables, was dominated by the effect of specimen size, to the detriment of discerning meaningful differences in shape between individuals, which are *a priori* of greater interest, considering our goal of recognizing morphological differences between existing taxa (historically defined mostly by shape and ornament), if such differences exist. Sampled across an assemblage, ammonite specimens often show many orders of magnitude of size

variation, but a relatively small amount of morphological variation. PC1, reflecting specimen size, explained 90.5% of the total variation, and all of the clusters in the 2- or 3-cluster scenarios were distinguished nearly entirely by size (Supplementary Fig. 11), as expected given the dominance of size-related variation in the data. Despite the large emphasis on specimen size, the distribution of individuals within the morphospace for the “linear PCA” remained similar to the “main PCA” (main text Figs. 10 and 11); specimens with mature modifications still formed two visually distinct groups (Supplementary Fig. 11) and unornamented individuals (a variable not included in either PCA) still fell into the lower left quadrant of the PC1-PC2 morphospace (Supplementary Fig. 12). By incorporating size-standardized and dimensionless variables alongside the linear measurement variables in our “main PCA”, our PCA and clustering analyses (main text Figs. 10 and 11) were better-equipped to discriminate specimens based on morphological characteristics other than size alone.

Note that two apparent outliers in the PC1-PC2 morphospace (individuals plotting in the lower right quadrant; Supplementary Fig. 11) reflect uncertainty due to missing data for these individuals rather than a “real” discrimination of these two specimens. The shape of the confidence ellipses for the position of these two individuals in the morphospace, as determined via multiple imputation (Supplementary Fig. 5), illustrates that these specimens share an overlapping morphospace with the rest of the specimens that score positively on PC1, when uncertainty due to the imputation of missing values is considered.

“Shape PCA”: Results

The “shape PCA” included the same data subset as our “main PCA” (n=105 specimens), but incorporated only the size-standardized or dimensionless variables from the “main PCA,” as well as log(WH) as a representation of specimen size. There were a total of five included variables: log(WH), WW/WH, VW/WH, UWI, and WHER, with a total of 25.7% missing values across the dataset. For the “shape PCA,” the first four principal components each explained $\geq 10\%$ of the total variance in the data and collectively explained 95.6% of the total variance. PC1 from the “shape PCA” was analogous to PC2 from the “main PCA” and captured variation in conch “stoutness,” with WW/WH and VW/WH loading positively on this component (Supplementary Fig. 13); individuals with positive PC1 scores have stouter

whorls and wider venters. PC2 from the “shape PCA” captured variation in specimen size and variation in the tightness of coiling of the conch, with WH and UWI making the largest contributions to this PC; individuals with positive PC2 scores are larger and are relatively evolute. PC3 captured variation in whorl height expansion rates, with WHER loading positively on this component (Supplementary Fig. 14); individuals with positive PC3 scores have larger whorl height expansion rates. PC4 captured variation in the same variables as PC2 (WH and UWI), but instead of both loading positively (as for PC2), WH loaded negatively and UWI loaded positively on PC4.

For the “shape PCA” data, the most frequently-supported number of clusters was four (optimal under eight of 30 cluster validity indices), followed by three clusters (optimal under five of the cluster validity indices). The projection of the 3- and 4-cluster scenarios into the ordination space of our “shape PCA” are shown in Supplementary Figures 13 and 14. For clarity, we will refer to the specific clusters in each of the “linear PCA” scenarios using the names assigned to them in Supplementary Figures 13 and 14.

“Shape PCA”: Discussion

The “shape PCA” included variables emphasizing variation in specimen shape (as opposed to variation in specimen size, which dominated the morphospace in the “linear PCA”). One variable representing specimen size (log-transformed WH) was still included in the “shape PCA” for two reasons: (1) sexual dimorphism is commonly characterized by differences in adult size for ammonites (Klug et al. 2015 and references therein), so including a representation of specimen size in the analysis is important for recognizing and interpretation potential sexual size dimorphism; and (2) our sample of specimens represents a range of ontogenetic stages (including both juveniles and specimens with mature modifications), so size provides critical context for interpreting patterns across the entire sample.

Problems with imputation of missing data for the “shape PCA”

One disadvantage of the “shape PCA” version, for our data, is that the exclusion of most of the linear measurement variables drastically reduced the patterns of covariation between the variables in the analysis, which diminished the performance of the regularized iterative PCA algorithm (Josse and Husson

2016) used to impute missing data (see main text Section 3.3.5. “Imputation of Missing Data”). PCAs and PCA-based approaches to data imputation perform best when there are strong correlations between variables (Josse and Husson 2012b; Hammer and Harper 2006). The data imputation approach of Josse and Husson (2016) requires an initial step to determine the “tuning parameter,” (called “ncp” in MissMDA package for R), which is the optimal number of components to use in the regularized iterative PCA algorithm to impute missing data. This parameter is determined via generalized cross-validation seeking to minimize the resulting mean square error of prediction (Josse and Husson 2016). For our “shape PCA”, the optimal number of components (ncp) was zero, which means that subsequent data imputation is performed using the “mean substitution” method, where each missing value is replaced with the mean value for that variable in the dataset, rather than with the full regularized iterative PCA algorithm (Josse and Husson 2012a). The method of “mean substitution” for missing data imputation tends to underestimate the variation in a dataset, resulting in some data homogenization (Clavel et al. 2014), which is counter to our goal of distinguishing potentially meaningful differences between individuals (e.g., taxa or sexual dimorphs, etc.), if such differences exist. The “shape PCA” may therefore have limited utility for interpreting inter-specimen differences, compared to our “main PCA.” This caveat may not apply to datasets derived from specimens with a higher degree of physical preservation and lower proportions of missing measurement data.

Similarities with the “main PCA”

The distribution of individuals within the PC1-PC2 morphospace for the “shape PCA” remained similar to the “main PCA” with two notable exceptions: (1) more individuals fell near the center of the morphospace in the “shape PCA” (a result of “mean substitution” imputation), and (2) specimen size loaded on PC2 of the “shape PCA” instead of on PC1 as for the “main PCA.” To better illustrate the similarities between the “shape PCA” and “main PCA” morphospaces, we plot PC2 on the x-axis and PC1 on the y-axis for all of our visualizations of the “shape PCA” (Supplementary Figs. 13-16); this results in both PC1-PC2 morphospaces for the “shape PCA” and “main PCA” being oriented such that differences in size are oriented along the x-axis and differences in whorl “stoutness” (WW/WH and

VW/WH) are oriented along the y-axis. With this visualization of the “shape PCA”, it is possible to visually demonstrate how unornamented individuals (a variable not included in the PCA) still fell into the same region of the morphospace (among relatively smaller and more compressed individuals) as they did in the “main PCA” (see Supplementary Figs. 13 and 15; main text Figs. 10 and 13). The 3-cluster models of the “main PCA” and “shape PCA” data were similar; clusters s-A and s-C of the “shape PCA” were analogous to clusters A and C in the “main PCA,” with a separation mainly by specimen size, and secondarily, shape (WW/WH and VW/WH). Clusters s-D in the “shape PCA” and D in the “main PCA” both represented the smallest individuals, but cluster s-D included fewer individuals than cluster D and was most distinguished from other clusters on the basis of differences in WHER, a variable with low repeatability that may have limited utility for consistently distinguishing between individuals (see section below).

Problems with the 4-cluster scenario in the “shape PCA”

Although the clustering analysis of the “shape PCA” dataset best-supported an additional cluster (a 4-cluster scenario as opposed to a 2- or 3-cluster scenario for the “main PCA” dataset), the extra cluster was characterized mainly by differences in WHER; cluster s-C in a 3-cluster scenario was split into clusters s-E and s-F in a 4-cluster scenario, which were most clearly distinguished along PC3, which represents differences in WHER. As observed in our Linear Mixed Model (LMM) results, WHER had a relatively low repeatability (0.274; Supplementary Table 5), reflecting relatively high within-individual variation compared to between-individual variation, and indicating that this variable is probably not useful for reliably discriminating between individuals (see main text Section 5.6.2. “Variable Repeatability and Utility in Discriminating Morphological Groups”). For this reason, the 4-cluster scenario of the “shape PCA” dataset may not provide much additional information beyond those morphological differences captured by the simpler 3-cluster scenario.

Secondary “Ornament PCA”

We analyzed two subsets of our data with PCA: the first (“main PCA”) included conch morphology variables measured in all of our specimens (n=105 specimens; main text Figs. 10 and 11), and the second, “ornament PCA” (n=45 specimens; Supplementary Figs. 17 and 18), added ornament-related variables only measured in some individuals (those with preserved ornamentation). The “ornament PCA” included the same eight variables as the first PCA and added six variables describing the position of umbilical and lateral tubercles (as linear measurements: UND, DUNU, DLNU; and as size-standardized variables: UND/WH, DUNU/WH, DLNU/WH), for a total of 14 variables. Specimens included in the “ornament PCA” were those with a position on the conch where both umbilical and lateral tubercles (UTs and LTs) were observed, and where at least one of three ornament variables (UND, DUNU, or DLNU) could be measured. These criteria resulted in a sample size of 45 specimens, and a dataset with a total of 25.6% missing values.

“Ornament PCA” results

For the “ornament PCA,” the first three principal components were retained; each explained $\geq 10\%$ of the total variance in the data and collectively they explained 86.2% of the total variance. Like our “main PCA” (main text Figs. 10 and 11), PC1 for the “ornament PCA” was influenced mostly by specimen size (Supplementary Fig. 17). PC2 was associated with WW/WH, VW/WH, WHER, UWI, and UND/WH, reflecting a combination of variables relating to overall conch shape, and the relative spacing of UT; individuals with positive PC2 scores have more widely spaced UT, stouter whorl shapes, relatively wider venters, and relatively more evolute conchs. PC3 was associated with the relative position of umbilical and lateral tubercles (Supplementary Fig. 18); all three size-standardized Wolleben (1967) variables (UND/WH, DUNU/WH, and DLNU/WH) loaded positively onto PC3.

For the “ornament PCA” data, the most frequently-supported number of clusters was two (optimal under nine of the 30 cluster validity indices). The projection of the 2-cluster scenario into the ordination space of our “ornament PCA” is shown in Supplementary Figures 17 and 18. For clarity here, we will refer to specific clusters of the “ornament PCA” using the names assigned to them in Supplementary Figures 17 and 18.

“Ornament PCA” 2-cluster model

The 2-cluster model received the most support (from nine of 30 cluster validity indices; see main text Section 3.3.6. “Clustering Analysis”). As for our “main PCA” data subset (main text Figs. 10 and 11), the two clusters for the “ornament PCA” data were mainly distinguished based on the overall size of the specimens (Supplementary Fig. 17C). The two clusters partially overlapped when projected onto PC2 and PC3, but showed some differentiation along PC2, with the individuals scoring highest on PC2 belonging to cluster orn-B (smaller, with stouter whorl shape, wider relative venter width, relatively more evolute, and relatively more distance between consecutive UTs), and the individuals scoring lowest belonging to cluster orn-A (larger, with more compressed whorl shape, narrower relative venter width, relatively more involute, and closer relative spacing of UTs). Just as for our “main PCA” (see main text Fig. 12), both clusters included individuals from all horizons, and individuals with both *Stantonoceras* and *Placentoceras* genus identifications (Supplementary Fig. 19).

Ornament position variables: limited contribution to the morphospace

Clustering of our secondary PCA, the “ornament PCA” (Supplementary Figs. 17 and 18) failed to discriminate any additional clusters despite the inclusion of six additional variables (UND, DUNU, DLNU, and each of their size-standardized versions). Variables relating to ornament position on the flanks may not be useful in discriminating between specimens of *Placentoceras* beyond the differences already identified using variables of conch morphology in our “main PCA.” Notably, UND and UND/WH were flagged by our LMM analyses as being unlikely to consistently discriminate between individuals due to a relatively high amount of within-individual variation (i.e., low repeatability; see main text Section 5.6.2. “Variable repeatability”). Additionally, DLNU was a remarkably homogenous variable across our data, with a unimodal distribution (main text Fig. 4H) and a monophasic isometric scaling relationship (main text Fig. 7B), suggesting that this variable is also unlikely to provide any meaningful discrimination between specimens. The only remaining variables novel to our “ornament PCA” were DUNU and DUNU/WH, which exhibit change over time (see main text Section 4.2.3. “Morphological Change Across Geological Time” and Section 5.4. “Temporal Changes in Morphology”).

Reliability of using multiple imputation to fill in missing data for PCA

We used the graphical approach recommended by Josse and Husson (2016) to evaluate the impact of the estimated missing values on the results of each PCA. The effect of the imputation on the resulting positions of individuals in ordinated space is visually evaluated by plotting the results of multiple imputation as a supplementary projection onto the PCA produced using the regularized iterative algorithm, in the form of confidence ellipses illustrating the variability in the position of each individual across all 200 iterations of the multiple imputation (see Supplementary Figs. 3, 5, and 7). Likewise, a supplementary projection of the variables from the multiple imputation enables a visual evaluation of the variation in the resulting variable vector position (Josse and Husson 2016; see Supplementary Figs. 4, 6, and 8).

The procedure used to fill in missing values for our “main PCA” and “ornament PCA” data subsets (the regularized iterative PCA algorithm of Josse and Husson (2016); see main text Section 3.3.5. “Imputation of Missing Data”) had minimal effects on analysis outcomes: projecting specimens onto PC1 and PC2 under 200 iterations of the regularized iterative PCA algorithm shows that the resulting individual variability ellipses are relatively small compared to the overall morphospace occupied by the entire sample of specimens (Supplementary Figs. 3, 5, and 7). Notably, there is little to no overlap of variability ellipses between individuals belonging to cluster A with those belonging to cluster B (2-cluster model of our “main PCA”; see main text Fig. 10C and Supplementary Fig. 3). Likewise, the projection of the original morphological variables onto PC1 and PC2 is stable across iterations (Supplementary Fig. 4), confirming that the loadings of the morphological variables onto the principal components are not sensitive to our missing values.

Supplementary Tables

		WW (whorl width)		WW/WH (whorl shape)	
Single Slope LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	-0.425 [-0.503, -0.340]	< 0.001	-0.425 [-0.504, -0.346]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	1.094 [1.043, 1.143]	< 0.001	0.094 [0.044, 0.139]	<0.001
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.006	0.751	0.006	0.751
	Residual	0.002		0.002	
	Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c
		0.896	0.974	0.060	0.766
Threshold LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	-0.646 [-0.764, -0.528]	<0.001	-0.646 [-0.758, -0.532]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	1.249 [1.171, 1.324]	<0.001	0.249 [0.173, 0.323]	<0.001
	WH (slope after threshold)	0.933 [0.852, 1.013]	<0.001	-0.067 [-0.148, 0.013]	0.103
	Threshold (mm WH)	41 [37.118, 48.304]	NA	41 [37.118, 48.304]	NA
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.006	0.787	0.006	0.787
Residual	0.002		0.002		
Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	
		0.895	0.978	0.095	0.807
Sample Size	n			n	
Specimens		99		99	
Observations		232		232	
Model Comparison	Model Deviance	<i>LogL</i>	<i>P</i>	Model Deviance	<i>LogL</i>
Single Slope LMM		-585.82		-585.82	
Threshold LMM		-609.97	< 0.001	-609.97	< 0.001

Supplementary Table 1. Table comparing linear mixed model (LMM) results for two response variables: a linear measurement variable (WW), and its size-standardized version (WW/WH); see Supplementary Figure 1. Response and explanatory variables were log-transformed before analysis. For both response variables, the results of the single-slope “Random Intercept Model” and the biphasic “Threshold Model” are compared. The repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each conch, not a taxonomic identification). Marginal R^2 values (R^2_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH), and conditional R^2 values (R^2_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). The model comparison section reports the results of the likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of the single slope “Random Intercept Model” versus the “Threshold Model,” including the deviance for each model and associated p-value (*P*) for the chi-squared statistic.

Response Variable	Model	WH (fixed effect)		Variance components			Model Comparison			
		Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	$V_{specimen}$	V_{WH}	$cov(specimen, WH)$	Model Deviance	Test	<i>LogL</i> Test Stat.	<i>P</i>
WW	1	1.094 [1.041, 1.145]	<0.001	0.006			-585.82			
	2	1.107 [1.042, 1.172]	<0.001	0.048	0.022	-0.940	-592.68	1 vs. 2	6.87	0.021
R	1	1.031 [1.003, 1.059]	<0.001	0.001			-539.13			
	2	1.029 [0.984, 1.073]	<0.001	0.039	0.014	-1.000	-566.55	1 vs. 2	27.41	< 0.001
VW	1	1.102 [1.015, 1.196]	<0.001	0.025			-273.27			
	2	1.091 [0.972, 1.215]	<0.001	0.125	0.072	-0.930	-289.39	1 vs. 2	16.12	< 0.001
RUWI	1	0.086 [-0.022, 0.198]	0.121	0.013			-217.17			
	2	0.095 [-0.083, 0.269]	0.276	0.547	0.200	-1.000	-245.14	1 vs. 2	27.97	< 0.001
WHER	1	-0.018 [-0.091, 0.052]	0.606	0.003			-301.36			
	2	-0.027 [-0.097, 0.040]	0.470	0.025	0.005	-0.950	-301.91	1 vs. 2	0.56	0.606

Supplementary Table 2. Comparison of alternative variance component structures for each morphological response variable. Model 1 refers to our “Random Intercept Model,” where specimen identity is included as a random intercept, and Model 2 refers to our “Random Slope Model,” evaluating support for specimen-specific growth patterns. Note that “specimen identity” refers to a unique identifier for each specimen, not to a taxonomic identification. The “WH (fixed effect)” column reports the estimated slope of each response variable on WH (a log-log relationship) across all individual specimens in the sample. The “variance components” column includes the variance associated with the random intercept ($V_{specimen}$) and random slope (V_{WH}), and the covariance of the random intercept and random slope (“ $cov(specimen, WH)$ ”). The model comparison columns report the results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the two models, including the deviance for each model, and the resulting chi-squared statistic (*LogL* Test Stat.) and associated p-value (*P*), which was adjusted using the method of Zuur et al. (2009). Response variables not included in this table did not have enough repeated measures to allow the “Random Slope Model” to converge.

		D (diameter)		R (radius)		U (umbilical width)		WW (whorl width)		VW (venter width)					
Random Intercept LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>				
	Intercept	0.235 [0.170, 0.297]	<0.001	0.047 [0.000, 0.100]	0.051	-0.551 [-0.801, -0.305]	<0.001	-0.425 [-0.503, -0.340]	<0.001	-1.132 [-1.276, -0.977]	<0.001				
	Whorl Height (WH)	1.056 [1.019, 1.092]	<0.001	1.031 [1.000, 1.058]	<0.001	1.118 [0.982, 1.260]	<0.001	1.094 [1.043, 1.143]	<0.001	1.102 [1.010, 1.189]	<0.001				
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.				
	Specimen ID	0.001	0.588	0.001	0.675	0.019	0.846	0.006	0.751	0.025	0.857				
	Residual	0.001		0.000		0.004		0.002		0.004					
Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c					
		0.984	0.994		0.988	0.996		0.833	0.974		0.896	0.974		0.651	0.950
Threshold LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>				
	Intercept	0.184 [0.113, 0.248]	<0.001	0.156 [0.084, 0.223]	<0.001	-0.658 [-0.905, -0.404]	<0.001	-0.646 [-0.764, -0.528]	<0.001	-1.320 [-1.497, -1.138]	<0.001				
	WH (slope before threshold)	1.087 [1.049, 1.126]	<0.001	0.957 [0.914, 1.006]	<0.001	1.184 [1.039, 1.327]	<0.001	1.249 [1.171, 1.324]	<0.001	1.238 [1.120, 1.354]	<0.001				
	WH (slope after threshold)	0.839 [0.689, 0.990]	<0.001	1.101 [1.054, 1.148]	<0.001	0.659 [0.068, 1.250]	0.033	0.933 [0.852, 1.013]	<0.001	0.730 [0.517, 0.943]	<0.001				
	Threshold (mm WH)	123 [109.98, >127]	NA	51 [40.924, 73.226]	NA	124 [<25, >131]	NA	41 [37.118, 48.304]	NA	45 [37.798, 57.363]	NA				
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.				
Specimen ID	0.001	0.521	0.001	0.751	0.017	0.823	0.006	0.787	0.024	0.857					
Residual	0.001		0.000		0.004		0.002		0.004						
Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c					
		0.986	0.993		0.987	0.997		0.845	0.973		0.895	0.978		0.647	0.950
Sample Size	n		n		n		n		n						
Specimens	43		36		44		99		93						
Observations	73		119		82		232		188						
Model Comparison	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>					
Single Slope LMM	-279.34		-539.13		-128.23		-585.82		-273.27						
Threshold LMM	-287.56	0.004	-551.52	<0.001	-130.72	0.114	-609.97	<0.001	-287.11	<0.001					

Supplementary Table 3. Linear mixed model (LMM) results for response variables representing linear measurements of conch morphology, contrasting the results of the single-slope “Random Intercept Model” and the biphasic “Threshold Model.” Response and explanatory variables were log-transformed before analysis. Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each conch, not a taxonomic identification). Marginal R^2 values (R^2_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH), and conditional R^2 values (R^2_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (*P*) for the chi-squared statistic. Confidence intervals for the position of the threshold were not able to be estimated in cases where they exceeded the boundaries of the range of possible threshold values tested (see main text Section 3.3.2. “Bivariate Analyses: Linear Mixed Models”).

		DSV (septal spacing)		UND		DUNU		DLNU	
Random Intercept LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>						
	Intercept	-0.536 [-0.746, -0.341]	<0.001	-0.612 [-0.790, -0.439]	<0.001	-1.280 [-1.597, -0.983]	<0.001	-0.218 [-0.325, -0.112]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	0.980 [0.856, 1.118]	<0.001	1.110 [1.012, 1.217]	<0.001	1.396 [1.216, 1.583]	<0.001	1.064 [0.997, 1.132]	<0.001
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.007	0.758	0.004	0.402	0.018	0.751	0.001	0.559
	Residual	0.002		0.006		0.006		0.001	
Variance Explained by the Model		R ² _m	R ² _c						
		0.774	0.945	0.893	0.936	0.823	0.956	0.966	0.985
Threshold LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>						
	Intercept	-0.355 [-0.674, -0.038]	0.033	-0.922 [-1.208, -0.638]	<0.001	-1.634 [-1.957, -1.325]	<0.001	-0.277 [-0.407, -0.153]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	0.854 [0.632, 1.067]	<0.001	1.315 [1.135, 1.498]	<0.001	1.630 [1.443, 1.830]	<0.001	1.103 [1.023, 1.184]	<0.001
	WH (slope after threshold)	1.095 [0.889, 1.300]	<0.001	0.823 [0.584, 1.062]	<0.001	0.308 [-0.251, 0.867]	0.286	0.874 [0.613, 1.136]	<0.001
	Threshold (mm WH)	37 [<24, >50]	NA	59 [29.157, 90.509]	NA	75 [63.854, 84.166]	NA	68 [<29, >68]	NA
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
Specimen ID	0.007	0.792	0.003	0.347	0.015	0.762	0.001	0.663	
Residual	0.002		0.006		0.005		0.001		
Variance Explained by the Model		R ² _m	R ² _c						
		0.768	0.952	0.906	0.938	0.853	0.965	0.964	0.988
Sample Size		n		n		n		n	
Specimens		50		45		42		32	
Observations		67		67		70		47	
Model Comparison		Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>						
Single Slope LMM		-143.28		-127.65		-89.52		-171.71	
Threshold LMM		-145.16	0.171	-134.35	0.010	-104.24	< 0.001	-173.52	0.179

Supplementary Table 4. Linear mixed model (LMM) results for response variables representing linear measurements of septal spacing and ornament position parameters, contrasting the results of the single-slope “Random Intercept Model” and the biphasic “Threshold Model.” Response and explanatory variables were log-transformed before analysis. Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each conch, not to a taxonomic identification). Marginal R² values (R²_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH), and conditional R² values (R²_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports the results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (*P*) for the chi-squared statistic. Confidence intervals for the position of the threshold

were not able to be estimated in cases where they exceeded the boundaries of the range of possible threshold values tested (see main text Section 3.3.2. “Bivariate Analyses: Linear Mixed Models”).

		UWI		RUWI		WHER		WRER	
Random Intercept LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	-0.829 [-1.017, -0.621]	<0.001	-0.860 [-1.045, -0.655]	<0.001	0.333 [0.202, 0.455]	<0.001	0.191 [0.074, 0.307]	0.003
	Whorl Height (WH)	0.086 [-0.024, 0.193]	0.117	0.086 [-0.035, 0.197]	0.121	-0.018 [-0.090, 0.057]	0.606	0.062 [-0.003, 0.127]	0.075
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.012	0.861	0.013	0.735	0.003	0.296	0.002	0.312
	Residual	0.003		0.005		0.008		0.004	
Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c		R^2_m	R^2_c		R^2_m	R^2_c	
		0.045	0.867	0.032	0.743	0.002	0.297	0.053	0.348
Threshold LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	-0.921 [-1.130, -0.690]	<0.001	-0.579 [-0.816, -0.308]	<0.001	-0.783 [-1.788, 0.107]	0.103	-0.207 [-0.695, 0.291]	0.392
	WH (slope before threshold)	0.142 [0.014, 0.256]	0.021	-0.099 [-0.274, 0.053]	0.222	0.839 [0.163, 1.608]	0.023	0.354 [-0.002, 0.716]	0.047
	WH (slope after threshold)	-0.304 [-0.778, 0.171]	0.215	0.331 [0.122, 0.540]	0.002	-0.051 [-0.123, 0.022]	0.173	0.020 [-0.059, 0.100]	0.619
	Threshold (mm WH)	127 [<32, >127]	NA	62 [40.098, 78.570]	NA	21 [<21, 24.326]	NA	27 [<27, 78.524]	NA
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
Specimen ID	0.010	0.832	0.016	0.791	0.003	0.274	0.001	0.297	
Residual	0.002		0.004		0.008		0.003		
Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c		R^2_m	R^2_c		R^2_m	R^2_c	
		0.098	0.849	0.042	0.800	0.038	0.302	0.095	0.364
Sample Size	n			n		n		n	
Specimens	42			36		62		35	
Observations	72			119		170		83	
Model Comparison	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>		Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>	Model Deviance	<i>LogL P</i>
Single Slope LMM	-150.11			-217.17		-301.36		-210.57	
Threshold LMM	-152.85	0.098		-224.18	0.008	-306.96	0.018	-213.62	0.081

Supplementary Table 5. Linear mixed model (LMM) results for response variables representing dimensionless parameters of coiling tightness or whorl expansion rate, contrasting the results of the single-slope “Random Intercept Model” and the biphasic “Threshold Model.” Response and explanatory variables were log-transformed before analysis. Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each conch, not a taxonomic identification). Marginal R^2 values (R^2_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH), and conditional R^2 values (R^2_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects

(specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including the deviance for each model and associated p-value (*P*) for the chi-squared statistic. The confidence intervals for the position of the threshold were not able to be estimated in cases where they exceeded the boundaries of the range of possible threshold values tested (see main text Section 3.3.2. “Bivariate Analyses: Linear Mixed Models”).

Variable	SD
D (diameter)	0.044
R (radius)	0.035
U (umbilical width)	0.159
WW (whorl width)	0.087
VW (venter width)	0.155
DSV (septal spacing)	0.087
UND	0.104
DUNU	0.176
DLNU	0.042
WHER	0.104
WRER	0.073
UWI	0.118
RUWI	0.139

Supplementary Table 6. Standard deviation (SD) for each variable across the full dataset, used as the “medium” effect size for power analysis simulations (see Supplementary Figs. 9 and 10). For dimensionless variables (WHER, WRER, UWI, and RUWI), SD is the standard deviation of the log-transformed variable. For linear measurement variables, SD is the standard deviation of the log-transformed size-standardized variable.

		D (diameter)				R (radius)				U (umbilical width)			
Temporal Model	Factor Level	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)
		Ripley	-0.035 [-0.065, -0.007]	0.029	6	9	-0.005 [-0.034, 0.025]	0.735	5	16	-0.160 [-0.278, -0.034]	0.010	6
	Mooreville/Blufftown	-0.051 [-0.094, 0.001]	0.052	2	2	-0.059 [-0.103, -0.015]	0.013	2	6	-0.368 [-0.535, -0.192]	<0.001	2	4
	Eutaw/Mooreville	-0.032 [-0.054, -0.010]	0.008	11	23	-0.003 [-0.028, 0.020]	0.803	8	25	-0.085 [-0.168, 0.006]	0.072	11	24
	Eutaw			18	29			16	54			19	35

		WW (whorl width)				VW (venter width)				DSV (septal spacing)			
Temporal Model	Factor Level	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)
		Ripley	-0.118 [-0.237, 0.007]	0.059	2	5	-0.040 [-0.345, 0.278]	0.797	1	3			0
	Mooreville/Blufftown	-0.062 [-0.134, 0.005]	0.100	6	12	-0.187 [-0.335, -0.048]	0.008	6	12	-0.053 [-0.133, 0.033]	0.224	6	8
	Eutaw/Mooreville	-0.033 [-0.074, 0.009]	0.125	26	77	-0.056 [-0.135, 0.025]	0.165	26	65	0.032 [-0.032, 0.102]	0.327	13	20
	Eutaw			43	100			39	73			22	30

		UND				DUNU				DLNU			
Temporal Model	Factor Level	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)
		Ripley	-0.101 [-0.178, -0.029]	0.012	5	11	-0.164 [-0.284, -0.041]	0.013	5	11	-0.044 [-0.112, 0.026]	0.211	2
	Mooreville/Blufftown	-0.089 [-0.208, 0.026]	0.134	2	3	-0.032 [-0.201, 0.150]	0.722	2	3	-0.001 [-0.064, 0.068]	0.967	2	3
	Eutaw/Mooreville	0.005 [-0.058, 0.065]	0.882	8	14	0.046 [-0.048, 0.144]	0.356	9	17	-0.005 [-0.043, 0.032]	0.779	10	18
	Eutaw			20	28			17	28			10	15

Supplementary Table 7. Results of the fixed-effect multi-level factor (“geological formation”) component of the “Temporal Model” linear mixed models (LMMs) for response variables representing linear measurements of conch morphology, septal spacing, or ornament position parameters. Response and explanatory variables were log-transformed before analysis. Coefficients (β) and associated p-values (*P*) are not provided for the Eutaw Formation factor level, which was set as the base level (intercept value) for the multi-level factor (see main text Section 3.3.3. “Bivariate Analyses: Extending LMMs to Evaluate Temporal Patterns”). Thus, β values capture mean differences in morphology between specimens from the Eutaw Formation and specimens from the Ripley, Mooreville/Blufftown, and Eutaw/Mooreville formations, respectively, while controlling specimen size (WH was an additional fixed effect predictor). Sample sizes (n) of individual specimens (inds.) and total number of observations (obs.) are listed for each factor level.

		WHER				WRER			
Temporal Model	Factor Level	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)
		Ripley	0.002 [-0.068, 0.067]	0.961	6	19	-0.041 [-0.099, 0.014]	0.162	5
	Mooreville/Blufftown	0.052 [-0.035, 0.140]	0.232	5	8	-0.017 [-0.105, 0.062]	0.680	2	4
	Eutaw/Mooreville	0.039 [-0.006, 0.086]	0.118	16	53	0.030 [-0.021, 0.079]	0.242	7	17
	Eutaw			26	68			16	38

		UWI				RUWI			
Temporal Model	Factor Level	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)	β [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	n (inds.)	n (obs.)
		Ripley	-0.117 [-0.208, -0.028]	0.018	6	9	0.000 [-0.131, 0.127]	0.997	5
	Mooreville/Blufftown	-0.271 [-0.408, -0.130]	0.001	2	2	-0.254 [-0.430, -0.076]	0.012	2	6
	Eutaw/Mooreville	-0.056 [-0.134, 0.018]	0.141	11	23	-0.005 [-0.110, 0.096]	0.925	8	25
	Eutaw			17	28			16	54

Supplementary Table 8. Results of the fixed-effect multi-level factor (“geological formation”) component of the “Temporal Model” linear mixed models (LMMs) for response variables representing dimensionless parameters of whorl expansion rate or coiling tightness. Response and explanatory variables were log-transformed before analysis. Coefficients (β) and associated p-values (*P*) are not provided for the Eutaw Formation factor level, which was set as the base level (intercept value) for the multi-level factor (see main text Section 3.3.3. “Bivariate Analyses: Extending LMMs to Evaluate Temporal Patterns”). Thus, β values capture mean differences in morphology between specimens from the Eutaw Formation and specimens from the Ripley, Mooreville/Blufftown, and Eutaw/Mooreville formations, respectively, while controlling specimen size (WH was an additional fixed effect predictor). Sample sizes (n) of individual specimens (inds.) and total number of observations (obs.) are listed for each factor level.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Results of linear mixed models (LMMs) fit to linear measurement response variables (panel A, shown for whorl width; WW) versus size-standardized versions (panel B, WW/WH) conform to expectations from the relationship of Eq. 2 to Eq. 5 (Supplement text, above). Black lines show the scaling relationship predicted by the best-fitting LMM for WW and WW/WH; grey envelopes depict the 95% confidence interval. The dotted red line in panel A depicts an isometric slope of 1 through the origin, for visual comparison. The position of the threshold for the biphasic scaling relationship is indicated by a vertical line (panels A and B), with vertical dashed lines indicating the 95% confidence interval for the threshold position. Model predictions are plotted on top of the raw data, with datapoint shape indicating the geological formation from which the specimen was collected. Datapoints labeled “Eutaw/Mooreville” indicate specimens collected without precise information from localities where both the Eutaw Formation and Mooreville Chalk are exposed.

Supplementary Figure 2. Comparison of the results of the main PCA (analysis using conch morphology variables and a dataset of 105 *Placenticerus* specimens; see main text Figures 10 and 11) when only linear measurement variables are log-transformed prior to the analysis (shown in panels A and B), versus when all variables (including dimensionless variables) are log-transformed prior to the analysis (shown in panels C and D). Panels A and C compare the impact of log-transforming only linear measurement variables versus all variables on the resulting morphospace projected onto the first two principal components; panels B and D make the same comparison for the projection onto the second and third principal components.

Supplementary Figure 3. Visual evaluation of the impact of filling in missing values on the resulting position of individuals in the morphospace of our main PCA (dataset of conch morphology variables and 105 *Placenticeras* specimens; see main text Figure 10) using the “supplementary projection” approach of Josse and Husson (2016). The datapoints represent the positions of individual specimens projected onto the first two principal components of the PCA morphospace, and the confidence ellipses illustrate the variability in the position of each individual across 200 iterations of the multiple imputation.

Supplementary Figure 4. Visual evaluation of the impact of filling in missing values on the resulting variable loadings for our main PCA (dataset of conch morphology variables and 105 *Placenticas* specimens; see main text Figure 10), using the “supplementary projection” approach of Josse and Husson (2016). The correlation circle illustrates the loadings of the variables in relation to the first two principal components (each shown as black vectors), and the cloud of colored datapoints for each variable depicts the variation in vector strength and position across 200 iterations of the multiple imputation.

Supplementary Figure 5. Visual evaluation of the impact of estimated missing values on the resulting position of individuals in the morphospace of our “linear PCA” (see Supplementary Figure 11), using the “supplementary projection” approach of Josse and Husson (2016). The datapoints represent the positions of individual specimens projected onto the first two principal components of the PCA morphospace, and the confidence ellipses illustrate the variability in the position of each individual across 200 iterations of the multiple imputation.

Supplementary Figure 6. Visual evaluation of the impact of estimated missing values on the resulting variable loadings for our “linear PCA” (see Supplementary Figure 11), using the “supplementary projection” approach of Josse and Husson (2016). The correlation circle illustrates the loadings of the variables in relation to the first two principal components (each shown as black vectors), and the cloud of colored datapoints for each variable depicts the variation in vector strength and position across 200 iterations of the multiple imputation.

Supplementary Figure 7. Visual evaluation of the impact of estimated missing values on the resulting position of individuals in the morphospace of our secondary PCA (“ornament PCA”; dataset of conch morphology and ornament position variables and 45 *Placenticeras* specimens), using the “supplementary projection” approach of Josse and Husson (2016). The datapoints represent the positions of individual specimens projected onto the first two principal components of the PCA morphospace, and the confidence ellipses illustrate the variability in the position of each individual across 200 iterations of the multiple imputation.

Supplementary Figure 8. Visual evaluation of the impact of estimated missing values on the resulting variable loadings for our “ornament PCA” (dataset of conch morphology and ornament position variables and 45 *Placenticer* specimens), using the “supplementary projection” approach of Josse and Husson (2016). The correlation circle illustrates the loadings of the variables in relation to the first two principal components (each shown as black vectors), and the cloud of colored datapoints for each variable depicts the variation in vector strength and position across 200 iterations of the multiple imputation.

Supplementary Figure 9. Results of power analysis simulations of the “Temporal Models” for each linear measurement response variable. Power, on the y-axis, was calculated as the proportion of 1,000 simulations with a statistically significant coefficient estimate (β) for a given number of Ripley specimens (n) and effect size. The four effect sizes are different multipliers of SD, the standard deviation of the log-transformed size-standardized response variable for each model (see Supplementary Table 6), and describe the change in each response variable from the oldest formation (Eutaw) to the youngest (Ripley; see details in main text Section 3.3.3. “Bivariate Analyses: Extending LMMs to Evaluate Temporal Patterns”). The horizontal red line highlights a threshold of 80% power. Vertical dashed lines indicate empirical numbers of specimens for the Ripley Formation (black) and for the Mooreville/Blufftown Formations (grey).

Supplementary Figure 10. Results of power analysis simulations of the “Temporal Models” for each linear measurement response variable. Power, on the y-axis, was calculated as the proportion of 1,000 simulations with a statistically significant coefficient estimate (β) for a given number of Ripley specimens (n) and effect size. The four effect sizes are different multipliers of SD, the standard deviation of the log-transformed response variable for each model (see Supplementary Table 6), and describe the change in each response variable from the oldest formation (Eutaw) to the youngest (Ripley; see details in main text Section 3.3.3. “Bivariate Analyses: Extending LMMs to Evaluate Temporal Patterns”). Symbolology as for Supplementary Figure 9.

Supplementary Figure 11. Results of the “linear PCA” and clustering analyses ($n=105$; incorporating only linear measurement variables, see Section 3.3.4. “Principal Component Analysis”), projected onto the first two principal components (PCs). (A) Specimens projected onto the morphospace of PC1 and PC2, with symbology indicating whether individuals exhibited mature modifications (a characteristic of adults), a body chamber but no discernable mature modifications, or were fully septate (no body chamber present); axis titles include the percent of the total variance in the data explained by each PC. (B) The correlation circle for the PCA, which shows the loadings of the original variables onto PC1 and PC2. (C-D) Results of the clustering analyses, projected into the morphospace of PC1 and PC2, with panels C and D depicting 2- and 3-cluster models, respectively. Clusters are assigned unique names for reference within the results and discussion. PC3 is not visualized because PC3 of the “linear PCA” represents only 0.9% of the total variance.

Supplementary Figure 12. Raw data of ornament presence/absence overlain on top of the individuals projected onto the first two components of the “linear PCA” (see Supplementary Fig. 11). A and B illustrate which specimens had umbilical tubercles at the measured conch position representing that individual in the PCA. Likewise, C and D indicate the type of lateral ornament present, if any, and E and F indicate which specimens had ventral tubercles. For C and D, lateral ornament is categorized as either a “true” tubercle (prominent node or bulla), or a swelling (subtle rib-like undulation that can be felt on the surface of the flank). Note that PC3 of the “linear PCA” represents only 0.9% of the total variance and is not visualized.

Supplementary Figure 13. Results of the “shape PCA” and clustering analyses ($n=105$; incorporating only WH and dimensionless or size-standardized variables, see Section 3.3.4. “Principal Component Analysis”), projected onto the first two principal components (PCs). (A) Specimens projected onto the morphospace of PC1 and PC2, with symbology indicating whether individuals exhibited mature modifications (a characteristic of adults), a body chamber but no discernable mature modifications, or were fully septate (no body chamber present); axis titles include the percent of the total variance in the data explained by each PC. (B) The correlation circle for the PCA, which shows the loadings of the original variables onto PC1 and PC2. (C,D) Results of the clustering analyses, projected into the morphospace of PC1 and PC2, with panels C and D depicting 3- and 4-cluster models, respectively. Clusters are assigned unique names for reference within the results and discussion. Note that for all panels (A-D), PC2 is on the x-axis and PC1 is on the y-axis.

Supplementary Figure 14. Results of the “shape PCA” and clustering analyses ($n=105$; incorporating only WH and dimensionless or size-standardized variables), projected onto the second and third principal components (PCs). (A) Specimens projected onto the morphospace of PC2 and PC3, with symbology as in Supplementary Figure 13. (B) The correlation circle for the PCA, which shows the loadings of the original variables onto PC2 and PC3. (C,D) Results of the clustering analyses, projected into the morphospace of PC2 and PC3, with panels C and D depicting 3- and 4-cluster models, respectively (the same cluster models depicted in Supplementary Figure 13). Note that, as for Supplementary Figure 13, all our clusters exist in multidimensional space, but are depicted here projected onto the two-dimensional space represented by two PC axes.

Supplementary Figure 15. Raw data of ornament presence/absence overlain on top of the individuals projected onto the first three components of the “shape PCA” (see Supplementary Fig. 13). A and B illustrate which specimens had umbilical tubercles at the measured conch position representing that individual in the PCA. Likewise, C and D indicate the type of lateral ornament present, if any, and E and F indicate which specimens had ventral tubercles. For C and D, lateral ornament is categorized as either a “true” tubercle (prominent node or bulla), or a swelling (subtle rib-like undulation that can be felt on the surface of the flank). Note that for the PC1-PC2 plots (panels A, C, E), PC2 is on the x-axis and PC1 is on the y-axis.

Supplementary Figure 16. Raw data of geological formation and prior taxonomic classification overlain on top of the individuals projected onto the first three principal components of the “shape PCA” (see Supplementary Fig. 13). A and B depict the geological formation each specimen was collected from, if known. Datapoints labeled “Eutaw/Mooreville” indicate specimens without precise horizon information from localities where both the Eutaw Formation and Mooreville Chalk are exposed. C-F depict the genus or species name previously assigned to each specimen by past workers, as designated on specimen labels or catalog information in the collections where studied specimens are housed. The species designation “n. sp.” refers to the unnamed species that Dr. Keith Young defined in his unpublished manuscript on the ammonites of Alabama (see Supplement text). Note that for the PC1-PC2 plots (panels A, C, E), PC2 is on the x-axis and PC1 is on the y-axis.

Supplementary Figure 17. Results of the “ornament PCA” and clustering analyses using both conch morphology and ornament position variables and a dataset of 45 *Placenticeras* specimens (individuals with both umbilical and lateral tubercles present; see Supplement text), projected onto the first two principal components (PCs). (A) Specimens projected onto the morphospace of PC1 and PC2, with symbology indicating whether individuals exhibited mature modifications (a characteristic of adult individuals), a body chamber but no discernable mature modifications, or were fully septate (no body chamber present); axis titles include the percent of the total variance in the data explained by each PC. (B) The correlation circle for the PCA, which shows the loadings of the original variables on PC1 and PC2. (C) Results of the clustering analyses, projected into the morphospace of PC1 and PC2, depicting 2-cluster model. Clusters are assigned unique names for reference within the Supplement text.

Supplementary Figure 18. Results of the “ornament PCA” and clustering analyses using both conch morphology and ornament position variables and a dataset of 45 *Placenticer* specimens (individuals with both umbilical and lateral tubercles present; see Supplement text), projected onto the second and third principal components (PCs). (A) Specimens projected onto the morphospace of PC2 and PC3, with symbology as in Supplementary Figure 17. (B) The correlation circle for the PCA, which shows the loadings of the original variables on PC2 and PC3. (C) Results of the clustering analyses, projected into the morphospace of PC2 and PC3, depicting 2-cluster model (the same cluster model depicted in Supplementary Figure 17). Note that, as for Supplementary Figure 17, all our clusters exist in multidimensional space, but are depicted here projected onto the two-dimensional space represented by two PC axes.

Supplementary Figure 19. Raw data of geological formation and prior taxonomic classification overlain on the individuals projected onto the first three principal components of the “ornament PCA” (see Supplementary Figs. 17 and 18). A and B depict the geological formation each specimen was collected from, if known. Datapoints labeled “Eutaw/Mooreville” indicate specimens collected without precise horizon information from localities where both the Eutaw Formation and Mooreville Chalk are exposed. C-F depict the genus or species name previously assigned to each specimen by past workers, as designated on specimen labels or catalog information in the collections where the studied specimens are housed. The species designation “n. sp.” refers to the unnamed new species that Dr. Keith Young defined in his unpublished manuscript on the ammonites of Alabama (see Supplement text).

Supplementary Figure 20. Map showing the collection localities for individuals belonging to cluster A (red circles) or cluster B (blue triangles) in the 2-cluster scenario for our main PCA data (see main text Figures 10 and 11). Alabama county outlines are shown in dark grey, and counties in Mississippi or Georgia are shown in light grey.

Supplementary Figure 21. Map showing collection localities for individuals belonging to either cluster A, C, or D in the 3-cluster scenario for our main PCA data (see main text Figures 10 and 11). Red circles indicate localities where specimens belong to cluster A were collected, green triangles indicate localities where specimens belonging to cluster C were collected, and blue crosses indicate localities where specimens belonging to cluster D were collected. Alabama county outlines are shown in dark grey, and counties in Mississippi or Georgia are shown in light grey.

Supplementary Figure 22. Results of the linear mixed models (LMMs) depicting the scaling relationship between each response variable and whorl height (WH) on a log-log scale, for response variables representing linear measurements of conch morphology (diameter, D; radius, R; umbilical width, U; whorl width, WW; and venter width, VW). Black lines show the scaling relationship predicted by the

best-fitting LMM for each response variable; grey envelopes depict the 95% confidence interval. All plots are drawn with a 1:1 aspect ratio. A dotted red line depicts an isometric slope of 1 through the origin, for visual comparison. For biphasic scaling relationships, the position of the threshold is indicated by a vertical line, with vertical dashed lines indicating the 95% confidence interval for the threshold position. Each model is plotted on top of the raw data measurements, with datapoint color and shape indicating the genus and species name, respectively, previously assigned to the specimen by past workers, as indicated on specimen labels or catalog information in the collections where the studied specimens are housed. The species designation “n. sp.” refers to the unnamed new species that Dr. Keith Young defined in his unpublished manuscript on the ammonites of Alabama (see Supplement text).

Supplementary Figure 23. Results of the linear mixed models (LMMs) depicting the scaling relationship between each response variable and whorl height (WH) on a log-log scale, for response variables representing linear measurements of septal spacing (DSV) or ornament position (umbilical node distance, UND; distance from umbilical node to umbilical seam, DUNU; distance from lateral node to umbilical seam, DLNU). Black lines show the scaling relationship predicted by the best-fitting LMM for each response variable; grey envelopes depict the 95% confidence interval. Symbology as for Supplementary Figure 22.

Supplementary Figure 24. Results of the linear mixed models (LMMs) depicting the scaling relationship between each response variable and whorl height (WH) on a log-log scale, for response variables representing whorl expansion rates (whorl height expansion rate, WHER; whorl radius expansion rate, WRER) or measurements of coiling tightness (umbilical width index, UWI; radial umbilical width index, RUWI). Black lines show the scaling relationship predicted by the best-fitting LMM for each response variable; grey envelopes depict the 95% confidence interval. Symbology as for Supplementary Figure 22.

Supplementary Figure 25. Dot plots depicting the univariate distributions of conch size (A and B), size-standardized variables (C-H), and other dimensionless variables (I-L) for all observations (all measured positions of all specimens) included in the “Temporal Model” linear mixed models (LMMs). For each variable, data are binned according to factor level: E refers to specimens from the Eutaw Formation, E/M refers to specimens from the Eutaw/Mooreville (representing uncertainty in provenance), M/B refers to specimens from the Mooreville Chalk or Blufftown Formation (lateral equivalents), and R refers to the Ripley Formation. Datapoints colored according to geological formation. See main text for variable abbreviations.

Supplementary References

- Atabekyan, A. A., and F. K. Khakimov. 1976: Kampaniski i Maastrikhtskie ammonity sredney Azii (Campanian and Maastrichtian Ammonites of Middle Asia). Donish, Dushanbe.
- Bardhan, S., T. K. Gangopadhyay, and U. Mandal. 2002: How far did India drift during the Late Cretaceous?—*Placenticerias kaffrarium* Etheridge, 1904 (Ammonoidea) used as a measuring tape. *Sedimentary Geology* 147:193–217.
- Böhm, J. 1898: Ueber *Ammonites pedernalis* v. Buch. *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Geologischen Gesellschaft* 50:183–201.
- Clavel, J., G. Merceron, and G. Escarguel. 2014: Missing Data Estimation in Morphometrics: How Much is Too Much? *Systematic Biology* 63:203–218.
- Cobban, W. A. 1993: Diversity and Distribution of Late Cretaceous Ammonites, Western Interior, United States. Pp.435–451 in W. G. E. Caldwell and E. G. Kauffman, eds. *Evolution of the Western Interior Basin*. Geological Association of Canada.
- . 2016: A survey of the Cretaceous ammonite *Placenticerias* Meek, 1876, in the United States Western Interior, with notes on the earliest species from Texas. *Acta Geologica Polonica* 66:587–608.
- DeKay, J. E. 1828: Report on several fossil multilocular shells from the state of Delaware; with observations on a second specimen of the new fossil genus *Eurypterus*. *Annals of the Lyceum of Natural History* 2:273–279, pl. 5.
- Dockery III, D. T. 1991: The streptoneuran gastropods, exclusive of the *Stenoglossa*, *Ptenoglossa*, and *Heterostropha*, of the Coffee Sand (Campanian) of northeastern Mississippi. Dissertation, Tulane University, New Orleans, Louisiana, 296 p.
- Donovan, A. D., G. R. Baum, G. L. Blechschmidt, T. S. Loutit, C. E. Pflum, and P. R. Vail. 1988: Sequence Stratigraphic Setting of the Cretaceous-Tertiary Boundary in Central Alabama. Pp.299–307 in C. K. Wilgus, B. S. Hastings, H. Posamentier, J. Van Wagoner, C. A. Ross, and C. G. St. C. Kendall, eds. *Sea-Level Changes: An Integrated Approach*, SEPM Special Publication No. 42. The Society of Economic Paleontologists and Mineralogists.
- Dujardin, F. 1837: Mémoire sur les conches du sol en Touraine, et description des coquilles de la craie et des Faluns. *Mémoires de la Société géologique de France* 2:211–311, pls. 15–20.
- Gangopadhyay, T. K., and S. Bardhan. 2007: Ornamental Polymorphism in *Placenticerias kaffrarium* (Ammonoidea; Upper Cretaceous of India): Evolutionary Implications. Pp.97–120 in N. H. Landman, R. A. Davis, and R. H. Mapes, eds. *Cephalopods Present and Past: New Insights and Fresh Perspectives*. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Hammer, Ø., and D. A. T. Harper. 2006: *Paleontological Data Analysis*. Blackwell Publishing, Malden, MA.
- Harrell Jr., T. L., A. Pérez-Huerta, and G. Phillips. 2016: Strontium isotope age-dating of fossil shark tooth enameloid from the Upper Cretaceous Strata of Alabama and Mississippi, USA. *Cretaceous Research* 62:1–12.
- Hilgard, E. W. 1860: Report on the geology and agriculture of the State of Mississippi. E. Barksdale, Jackson, MS.
- Hyatt, A. 1903: Pseudoceratites of the Cretaceous. United States Geological Survey, Washington, D. C., 1–351 p., pls. 1–47.
- Iljin, V. D. 1958: New genus of ammonites from south western Uzbekistan. *Doklady Akademii Nauk SSSR* 121:727–729.
- . 1959: Stratigraphy of the Upper Cretaceous deposits of West Uzbekistan and adjacent regions of Turkmenia. *Trudy VNIGNI* 23:181–222; pls. 1–8.
- . 2000: Upper Cretaceous ammonites of the central regions of middle Asia (Hoplitaceae, Acanthocerataceae, Tissotiaceae, Desmocerataceae). *Bulletin of CF VNIGNI* 4:1–157.

- Johnson, D. W. 1903: The Geology of the Cerrillos Hills, New Mexico. Part II: Palaeontology. The School of Mines Quarterly 24:173–217, pls. 1–14.
- Josse, J., and F. Husson. 2012a: Handling missing values in exploratory multivariate data analysis methods. *Journal de la Société Française de Statistique* 153:79–99.
- . 2012b: Selecting the number of components in principal component analysis using cross-validation approximations. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis* 56:1869–1879.
- . 2016: **missMDA**: A Package for Handling Missing Values in Multivariate Data Analysis. *Journal of Statistical Software* 70.
- Kennedy, W. J. 1987: Ammonites from the type Santonian and adjacent parts of Northern Aquitaine, Western France. *Palaeontology* 30:765–782, pls. 80–82.
- Kennedy, W. J., and C. W. Wright. 1983: *Ammonites polyopsis* Dujardin, 1837 and the Cretaceous ammonite family Placenticeratidae Hyatt, 1900. *Palaeontology* 26:855–873, pls. 85–87.
- Kennedy, W. J., W. A. Cobban, and N. H. Landman. 1997: Campanian Ammonites from the Tombigbee Sand Member of the Eutaw Formation, the Mooreville Formation, and the Basal Part of the Demopolis Formation in Mississippi and Alabama. *American Museum Novitates*:1–44.
- Kennedy, W. J., W. A. Cobban, and G. R. Scott. 2000: Heteromorph ammonites from the Upper Campanian (Upper Cretaceous) *Baculites cuneatus* and *Baculites reesidei* zones of the Pierre Shale in Colorado, USA. *Acta Geologica Polonica* 50:1–20.
- Kennedy, W. J., J. M. Hancock, W. A. Cobban, and N. H. Landman. 2004: A revision of the ammonite types described in F. Roemer's "Die Kreidebildungen von Texas und ihre organischen Einschlüsse" (1852). *Acta Geologica Polonica* 54:433–445, pls. 1–4.
- Klingenberg, C. P. 2016: Size, shape, and form: concepts of allometry in geometric morphometrics. *Development Genes and Evolution* 226:113–137.
- Klinger, H. C., and W. J. Kennedy. 1989: Cretaceous faunas from Zululand and Natal, South Africa. The ammonite family Placenticeratidae Hyatt, 1900; with comments on the systematic position of the genus *Hypenonoceras* Spath, 1924. *Annals of the South African Museum* 98:241–408.
- Klug, C., M. Zatoń, H. Parent, B. Hostettler, and A. Tajika. 2015: Mature Modifications and Sexual Dimorphism. Pp.253–320 in C. Klug, D. Korn, K. De Baets, I. Kruta, and R. H. Mapes, eds. *Ammonoid Paleobiology: From Anatomy to Ecology*. Vol. 1. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Larson, N. L. 2016: The Late Cretaceous (upper Campanian) cephalopod fauna from the Coon Creek Science Center, McNairy County, Tennessee. *Bulletin of the Alabama Museum of Natural History* 33:21–58.
- Mancini, E. A., and T. M. Puckett. 2005: Jurassic and Cretaceous Transgressive-Regressive (T-R) Cycles, Northern Gulf of Mexico, USA. *Stratigraphy* 2:31–48.
- Mancini, E. A., B. H. Tew, and C. C. Smith. 1989: Cretaceous-Tertiary contact, Mississippi and Alabama. *The Journal of Foraminiferal Research* 19:93–104.
- Mancini, E. A., M. T. Puckett, and B. H. Tew. 1996: Integrated biostratigraphic and sequence stratigraphic framework for Upper Cretaceous strata of the eastern Gulf Coastal Plain, USA. *Cretaceous Research* 17:645–669.
- Morton, S. G. 1834: Synopsis of the Organic Remains of the Cretaceous Group of the United States. Illustrated by nineteen plates, to which is added an appendix, containing a tabular view of the Tertiary fossils hitherto discovered in North America. Key and Biddle, Philadelphia.
- Reeside, J. B., Jr. 1927: The cephalopods of the Eagle Sandstone and related formations in the Western Interior of the United States. in *Professional Paper*. U.S. Geological Survey, Washington, D.C., 1–87, pls. 1–45 p.
- Roemer, F. 1852: Die Kreidebildungen von Texas und ihre organischen Einschlüsse. Adolph Marcus, Bonn.
- Schwimmer, D. R., K. Padian, and A. B. Woodhead. 1985: First Pterosaur Records from Georgia: Open Marine Facies, Eutaw Formation (Santonian). *Journal of Paleontology* 59:674–676.

- Sealey, P. L., and S. G. Lucas. 2022: Late Cretaceous (Campanian-Maastrichtian) ammonites from the Pierre Shale, Raton Basin, northeastern New Mexico and southeastern Colorado. *New Mexico Museum of Natural History and Science Bulletin* 91:1–183.
- Sohl, N. F. 1964: Gastropods from the Coffee Sand (Upper Cretaceous) of Mississippi. *in Professional Paper*. U.S. Geological Survey, Washington, D. C., 345–394, pls. 53–57 p.
- Stephenson, L. W. 1914: Cretaceous deposits of the eastern Gulf region and species of *Exogyra* from the eastern Gulf region and the Carolinas. United States Geological Survey, Washington, D.C., 1–77 p.
- . 1923: Invertebrate fossils of the Upper Cretaceous formations. *North Carolina Geological and Economic Survey* 5:1–402, pls. 1–100.
- . 1941: The larger invertebrates of the Navarro Group of Texas (exclusive of corals and crustaceans and exclusive of the fauna of the Escondido Formation). *University of Texas Publication* 4101:1–641; pls. 1–95.
- . 1956: Fossils from the Eutaw Formation, Chattahoochee River Region, Alabama-Georgia. United States Geological Survey, Washington, D. C., 227–250 p., pls. 38–45.
- Stephenson, L. W., and W. H. Monroe. 1940: The Upper Cretaceous Deposits. Mississippi State Geological Survey, University, Mississippi, 1–296 p., pls. 1–15.
- Waggoner, K. J. 2006: Sutural form and shell morphology of *Placentiaceras* and systematic descriptions of Late Cretaceous ammonites from the Big Bend region, Texas. Dissertation, Texas Tech University, Lubbock, Texas, 398pp.
- Wolleben, J. A. 1967: Senonian (Cretaceous) Mollusca from Trans-Pecos Texas and Northeastern Chihuahua, Mexico. *Journal of Paleontology* 41:1150–1165.
- Wright, C. W. 1996: Cretaceous Ammonoidea. *in* J. H. Calloman and M. K. Howarth, eds. *Treatise on Invertebrate Paleontology*. Vol. 4. The University of Kansas and The Geological Society of America, Boulder, Colorado.
- Young, K. 1963: Upper Cretaceous Ammonites from the Gulf Coast of the United States. Bureau of Economic Geology, The University of Texas, Austin, Texas.
- Zuur, A. F., E. N. Ieno, N. J. Walker, A. A. Saveliev, and G. M. Smith. 2009: Mixed Effects Models and Extensions in Ecology with R. *in Statistics for Biology and Health*. Springer, New York, NY.